

Load Balancing and Alternative Path Selection in Self-Organized Networks: A Data Plane Approach

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ABSTRACT This paper presents a novel load balancing algorithm tailored for deeply programmable networks, offering a decentralized approach to optimizing packet forwarding and load distribution. Unlike conventional systems reliant on centralized controllers or manual configurations, this algorithm operates entirely within the data plane, leveraging controlled flooding to dynamically discover and reroute traffic based on real-time congestion data. By detecting latency spikes indicative of congestion, switches autonomously select alternative paths to maintain optimal traffic flow. Implemented in the P4 data plane programming language, the algorithm is rigorously evaluated against existing load balancing methods for self-organized networks. The results demonstrate significant reductions in data transmission times, improved path symmetry, and enhanced scalability under various network conditions, making it a robust solution for modern, self-organized, and high-performance networks.

INDEX TERMS P4, programmable networks, load balancing, self-organized networks

I. INTRODUCTION

A. PROGRAMMABLE NETWORKS

The importance of software-defined networks (SDNs) [1] has grown significantly in the last decade. These networks operate by separating packet forwarding pipelines (data plane) from network control functions (control plane). This architectural division fosters innovation, shortens implementation timelines, and enables the development of high-speed, adaptable networks [2].

Communication between the data plane and the control plane introduces latency, especially when a centralized controller manages multiple devices. Implementing solutions entirely within the data plane allows algorithms to scale more effectively and react to events faster. Traditional data planes could only process pre-installed protocols [3], which limited innovation. To address these challenges, data plane programming has emerged, enabling the specification of complex packet processing procedures at a high level of abstraction.

Currently, the protocol-independent P4 [4] data plane programming language is widely used [5]. Standardized communication protocols between the control and data planes, along with compilers like T4P4S [6], ensure that P4 programs can be compiled for diverse target devices.

B. LOAD BALANCING

Switches handling an excessive number of packets can result in prolonged queues and additional latency within the network. Moreover, when queues become full, packet loss occurs, causing TCP flows to reduce their transmission rates, further delaying data delivery. In essence, when a switch is overloaded with packet forwarding responsibilities, the transmission time for data increases, leading to delays even for short messages. This issue can occur in scenarios such as where the network traffic of a facility exceeds the capabilities of a single switch (e.g. in data centers) or where sensors and IoT devices produce and transmit large amounts of data (e.g. in smart cities, or factory automation) [7] [8].

Various approaches have been developed to address network congestion. Active Queue Management (AQM) solutions aim to prevent switch queues from becoming excessively long by signaling TCP flows to decrease their transmission rates as queue lengths approach critical levels [9]. Another approach is load balancing, which ensures equal utilization of network resources, preventing any single switch from becoming overwhelmed. This balanced distribution of resources reduces congestion, lowers network latency, and increases maximum bandwidth.

However, not all networks use load balancing. For example, the Spanning Tree Protocol (STP) [10] deactivates redundant links to create a tree-like network topology, which simplifies packet forwarding but restricts paths between hosts to a single option, limiting load balancing capabilities.

The Equal-Cost Multi-Path (ECMP) method is a basic load balancing technique [11]. It selects one path from several equally favorable options for each flow, distributing flows across paths without considering their bandwidth requirements. This approach can inadvertently lead to congestion, especially in asymmetrical network topologies or when flows have varying bandwidth demands [12]. Additionally, ECMP does not identify possible paths between hosts; this task is typically handled by the control plane.

Many modern load balancing algorithms have emerged, with various strengths and weaknesses, making them ideal for different scenarios. They are further discussed in Section II.

C. SELF-ORGANIZED NETWORKS

Self-organized networks are defined as networks capable of autonomously forwarding packets without external configuration, centralized controllers, or knowledge of their own topology. In these networks, all switches operate using the same software. Most contemporary networks fall into this category, where switches dynamically learn the port associated with each MAC address, enabling the forwarding of both unicast and broadcast packets—a technique often referred to as *Transparent Bridging* [13].

Alternatively, if the network topology is predetermined, a centralized configuration can be used instead of relying on MAC learning. In such cases, a centralized controller uploads packet forwarding rules to switches, eliminating the need for autonomous learning. This paper focuses on self-organized networks due to the limitations of centrally configured ones.

D. CONTRIBUTION

This paper aims to present a load balancing algorithm that offers different (often improved) properties and performance compared to existing solutions applicable to self-organized programmable networks (discussed in Section II). Our proposed algorithm is based on controlled flooding and has the following characteristics, many of which are missing from alternative solutions:

- It can establish low-latency paths for packet forwarding in arbitrary network topologies without requiring a centralized controller or manual configuration.
- It remains functional even if data persistence temporarily fails, for example, due to hash collisions.
- It supports forwarding of both unicast and broadcast packets, and it can load balance any Ethernet-based protocol.
- It dynamically responds to changing network conditions by redirecting flows one by one to less congested routes until congestion is resolved.

- It ensures symmetric paths: communication between a pair of hosts uses the same path in both directions.
- It considers network latency in both directions of the symmetric paths, not just from client to server.
- The algorithm remains fully functional in scenarios such as (i) unidirectional UDP traffic (where the host receiving the packets does not send replies) and (ii) packet loss, even if control packets are lost.

The performance of this load balancing algorithm has been evaluated against various state-of-the-art solutions, including considerations for the traffic overhead it introduces. To demonstrate its practical feasibility, the algorithm has been implemented using the P4 data plane programming language, and the source code has been made publicly available¹.

II. RELATED WORK

There are numerous load balancing solutions, including those designed for programmable and/or self-organized networks.

The congestion avoidance solution presented in [14] switches to a pre-computed alternative path when congestion occurs on the main path. The control plane, responsible for determining these paths, is aware of the network's topology and state, such as load, which allows it to find optimal paths. When a switch detects that it is taking too long to process a packet (indicating congestion in the switch or its egress port), it redirects one of the traffic flows to the alternative path. If the switch is unaware of any alternative paths (for instance, because none exist at that point in the network topology), it will instruct the preceding switch to make the path change (which might, in turn, request the switch before it). The authors implemented the algorithm in the data plane using the P4 programming language, enabling fast detection and response to congestion. However, since the algorithm depends on a centralized controller, it is not suitable for self-organized networks.

In contrast, ARP-Path [15] is a path selection algorithm specifically designed for self-organized networks. Switches explore all possible paths between the ARP source and destination hosts using *ARP request* and *ARP reply* packets, but only the fastest path is learned and saved. As network latency tends to be higher on congested paths, this algorithm also serves as a load balancing solution. However, its primary limitation is that it only performs MAC-level load balancing (instead of e.g., flow-level). Moreover, learned paths are not updated if network load changes, which restricts the algorithm's ability to effectively balance load over time.

In [16], the authors generalize the ARP-Path algorithm into All-Path and examine its performance in greater detail, as well as its compatibility with other types of switches.

In [17], a load balancing algorithm called TCP-Path is introduced. Unlike ARP-Path, TCP-Path does not establish a path between pairs of hosts but learns a new path for each TCP connection, achieving more efficient load balancing. However, the feasibility of this algorithm in P4-

¹<https://github.com/Trigary/p4-self-organized-load-balancer>

programmable networks has not been investigated, and the learning process only considers network latency in the direction from the TCP client to the server, ignoring the load in the opposite direction.

The TRILL [18] and Shortest Path Bridging (SPB) [19] algorithms aim to replace the Spanning Tree Protocol. They learn paths between hosts and utilize ECMP load balancing when multiple paths are available: each packet is forwarded along the path corresponding to its hashed flow ID. However, these algorithms do not account for the bandwidth demand of flows or the load on switches, limiting their ability to balance loads effectively.

CONGA [20] is a more modern approach to load balancing, specifically designed for use in data centers. Instead of balancing loads at the flow level, the authors divide flows into *flowlets* (bursts of packets separated by pauses) and balance these smaller units to improve efficiency while avoiding packet reordering.

An improved version of CONGA, called HULA, is presented in [21]. The authors significantly reduce the algorithm's memory requirements, improving scalability. They also demonstrate that HULA can be implemented in programmable networks without the need for custom hardware.

Both CONGA and HULA can reroute the same flow multiple times during its lifetime, even if congestion is not present. While this behavior may not be problematic for data center traffic, it could cause issues in systems where flows have stateful components (e.g., middleware tracking cellular data usage). Frequent rerouting could lead to unnecessary data migration and increased server load.

BurstBalancer [22] is a load balancing solution designed to minimize flow disruptions. It applies dynamic path selection only to large flowlets that are critical for load balancing. Once a critical flowlet begins, a random egress port is selected for the remainder of the flowlet. Smaller, non-critical flows are not divided into flowlets, and their egress port remains unchanged; they are forwarded using ECMP.

Host-based load balancing solutions, which rely on custom host logic rather than custom switch logic, also exist. In [23], the authors introduce a custom TCP implementation that changes the IPv6 flow identifier when congestion is detected via ECN [24]. The network's switches use ECMP or WCMP [25] to select a path based on the hash of the flow identifier, allowing flows to be redirected to new paths whenever their identifier changes.

Another host-based solution is Meet [26], which uses flow RTT statistics and network probing to detect congestion. Hosts within the same server rack share this information and use it to select a congestion-free end-to-end path for each flowlet via XPath [27].

In [28], the authors propose using graph neural networks to predict network delays, which are then used to select forwarding paths and split long-lived flows into flowlets. Short-lived flows are forwarded along the best available path to ensure real-time performance, while long-lived flows

Solution	Support for unaltered hosts	Self-organized network support	Granularity of load balancing	Able to react to changed load	Considers network delay	Considers delay in both directions
[14]	✓	✗	Flow	✓	✓	✓
[15] [16]	✓	✓	MAC pair	✗	✓	✗
[17]	✓	✓	TCP flow	✗	✓	✗
[18] [19]	✓	✓	Flow	✗	✗	✗
[20] [21]	✓	✗	Flowlet	✓	✓	✓
[22]	✓	✗	Flowlet	✓	✗	✗
[23] [26]	✗	✗	TCP flowlet	✓	✓	✓
[28]	✓	✗	Flowlet	✓	✓	✓
Ours	✓	✓	Flow	✓	✓	✓

TABLE 1: Comparison of different load balancing solutions. Unless otherwise specified, flows and flowlets include both TCP and UDP protocols.

are distributed across multiple paths to prevent congestion caused by their extended presence on a single path.

Table 1 summarizes the key characteristics of various load balancing solutions. The table shows that our algorithm, unlike others supporting self-organized networks, can react to changing network conditions and considers latency in both traffic directions, without requiring modifications to hosts.

III. OUR PROPOSED MODEL

This section presents our proposed load balancing model, providing an overview of its objectives and a detailed description of its internal mechanics.

Our objective is to enable the forwarding of both unicast and broadcast/multicast packets within a network with an unknown topology, without relying on a centralized controller or manual switch configuration. The model aims to minimize packet loss and duplication while evenly distributing network traffic across multiple paths to maximize throughput and minimize latency. Our load balancing solution is designed for networks consisting of programmable switches running our algorithm and standard hosts. The model supports any network topology in which each host is connected to exactly one switch; the network can even contain loops. In fact, load balancing is only possible when such alternative paths (loops) exist. Since our algorithm requires no manual configuration, it operates primarily at the data link layer and implements MAC learning, enabling hosts to perform ARP learning.

The primary task of our load balancing solution is to avoid congestion by dynamically identifying uncongested paths and redirecting flows to them when impending congestion is detected on their current paths. Congestion occurs when the queue associated with a switch's egress port becomes saturated, leading to packet loss due to queue overflow. By mitigating congestion, we also achieve our broader goals of optimizing throughput and minimizing packet loss and queue delay (latency). In the following sections, we will explore the detailed workings of this load balancing solution.

A. BASIC PACKET FORWARDING

Our packet forwarding and load balancing solution employs two distinct types of path learning: flow-independent source MAC address learning and flow-specific path learning. The former, widely used in transparent bridging, is employed by our algorithm to forward broadcast/multicast packets and to handle cases where no flow-specific path has been established yet. The latter is applied whenever a flow-specific path is available.

Using MAC learning, we can forward unicast packets through a previously learned port, or use split horizon forwarding² for unicast and broadcast packets with an unknown (unlearned) destination MAC address. Our algorithm assumes that persistence (the learning of MAC addresses or flow-specific paths) may occasionally fail due to hash collisions or memory limitations. To prevent loops from forming, the algorithm only forwards packets once the source MAC address has been successfully learned. If this learning does not occur, a packet forwarded by one switch could be sent back to the same switch through a loop, causing the switch to associate an incorrect port with the packet's source MAC address. The complete packet forwarding process, including flow-specific components (discussed in Section III-D2), is illustrated in Figure 2.

B. FLOW IDENTIFICATION

For the load balancing solution to function effectively, it must be able to assign different paths to different flows. We use the following fields to differentiate between flows: source and destination MAC addresses, EtherType, source and destination IPv4 addresses, IP protocol, and source and destination UDP/TCP ports. If any of these fields are unavailable (because the packet lacks the corresponding headers), they are replaced with a constant value (e.g., 0). If a transport layer protocol other than UDP or TCP is used, our algorithm might mistakenly classify some distinct flows as a single flow, reducing the maximum efficiency of load balancing but not posing any other risks. When IPv6 is used instead of IPv4, this issue can be mitigated by using the *flow label* found in IPv6 headers [29].

To minimize the memory required to store flow identifiers, fields other than the MAC addresses (e.g., IP addresses, ports, and protocols) can be hashed. The impact of hash collisions is minimized by excluding MAC addresses from the hashing process: packets are forwarded to the correct host (MAC address) even when hash collisions occur. However, collisions can affect the algorithm's ability to differentiate between the flows of a particular host pair, potentially forcing multiple flows to share the same path. For a hash collision to occur with a probability of 0.1% when using a 32-bit hash, at least 2,931 simultaneous flows are required between a pair of hosts [30].

²Split horizon forwarding refers to forwarding a received packet through all ports except the ingress port.

FIGURE 1: Leaf port detection process in a topology where switch Y is connected to switch X and host A.

C. LEAF PORTS AND LEAF SWITCHES

We refer to the ports that connect switches directly to hosts as "leaf ports." Additionally, we define the switch directly connected to a host as the leaf switch for that host's MAC address. A flow involves communication between two MAC addresses, and we define the lower and upper leaf switches as the switches connected to the MAC address with the lower or higher numerical value, respectively, between the two.

Leaf switches play an essential role in our algorithm, as they coordinate the learning processes for a given flow. Since all switches run the same source code and there is no centralized controller, there is no natural "source of truth" in the network. By designating a leaf switch as the coordinator for a flow, we can ensure that multiple learning processes are not happening concurrently for the same flow.

To determine whether a switch is a leaf switch for a given host, it must identify whether it is directly or indirectly connected to that host. Upon switch startup, the switch sends a custom (non-standard) request packet through each port and waits for a reply. If no reply is received within a reasonable timeout, the port is classified as a leaf port. Switches immediately send a reply when they receive such a packet. Hosts, on the other hand, drop these packets, because they contain a MAC address that differs from the hosts' MAC. The leaf port identification process occurs during switch startup and is shown in Figure 1.

D. LEARNING FLOW-SPECIFIC PATHS

To achieve load balancing, we designed an algorithm that enables i) learning a separate path (route) for each flow, and ii) replacing the current path with a better one when congestion occurs. Once a path is learned for a flow, the ports saved in the flow's path entry during the learning process take precedence over the ports learned through MAC learning when forwarding that flow's packets. Figure 2 illustrates the packet forwarding process. The different conditions under which path learning is initiated are discussed in Section

FIGURE 2: The packet forwarding process. Actions that rely on MAC learning are shown in blue, while path entry-related actions are shown in green.

III-D1, while the learning process itself is explained in Section III-D2.

1) Starting Path Learning

A path learning process is required when one of the following conditions is met during packet processing:

- No path has been learned for the packet's flow. This typically happens when the flow has just started. An exception occurs when the switch is both the lower and upper leaf for the packet's flow: in this case, the only possible path involves a single switch, so no path learning is necessary.
- Congestion is detected on the switch (the egress port's queue is long), sufficient time has passed since the flow's current path was learned, and the grace period for this condition is inactive. This condition governs the load balancing function of the algorithm, while also preventing recently learned paths from being replaced too soon. The grace period ensures that flows are rerouted one at a time during congestion, while congestion is detected. A path learning process is not required if the packet's egress port is a leaf port, as no alternative paths exist in that case.
- No MAC learning entry has been persisted for the MAC address(es) of the packet's flow. This may occur if the persistence of the path entry succeeds, but MAC learning fails temporarily during the same packet's processing. MAC learning entries are essential to ensuring zero packet loss when a flow temporarily halts transmission.

During such pauses, the path entries for such flows may be deleted from some switches to free up memory. MAC learning entries ensure that packets arriving at these switches still reach their destination.

- An asymmetric path is detected, meaning that the current packet should have been received through a different port according to the learned path. Asymmetric paths indicate that packets take different routes in the forward and reverse directions between the two hosts, which may occur if the custom learning packets are dropped due to congestion.

When a condition is met at the lower leaf switch and no grace period is active, the switch can initiate the learning process. The grace period prevents concurrent learning processes for the same flow. Its duration depends on the maximum time it takes for a learning process to complete, which is the time required for a packet to traverse the network's longest path between the leaf switches, round-trip.

If a switch other than the lower leaf switch determines that path learning is necessary, it must request the lower leaf switch to initiate the process by sending a request packet (either directly or through intermediate switches). A grace period also applies in this case to prevent switches from continuously requesting learning processes while a previous request is still in progress.

It is important to emphasize that the frequency at which path changes can be requested depends on the size of the network: in larger networks the maximum round-trip time (maximum learning process duration) increases, requiring longer grace periods and decreasing the number of flows that can be rerouted within a certain time frame. However, larger networks consist of more switches that can request learning processes (with independent grace periods), potentially mitigating the issue of longer grace periods.

Sending the request packet is not always straightforward, as the port through which it should be sent or forwarded may be unknown. Using split horizon to send the request packet toward the lower leaf switch could lead to uncontrolled flooding³, which could impair the network's ability to forward host packets. Therefore, split horizon forwarding is only used when the switch itself makes the request. When the lower leaf switch receives a request packet (from a neighboring switch), it starts the learning process. If an intermediate switch knows the correct port to forward the request packet, it does so; otherwise, it drops the packet. Regardless, the learning process is guaranteed to begin because the switches in the path between the lower leaf switch and the requesting switch will either forward the packet or initiate a learning process themselves due to the unknown port. This mechanism ensures that a learning process starts when any switch requests it. The request packet's sending and handling algorithm is shown in Figure 3.

³Flooding is a method to propagate information across a network by utilizing split horizon forwarding at each switch. Uncontrolled flooding refers to flooding without proper termination checks, where network loops cause packets to be forwarded indefinitely within the loop.

FIGURE 3: The sending and handling of request packets. Actions dependent on path entries are shown in green.

2) The Learning Process

We implemented per-flow path learning using a custom Ethernet protocol. The algorithm utilizes controlled flooding to discover all possible paths between the lower and upper leaf switches in the network and eventually chooses and persists the optimal one. The leaf switches can complete packet delivery by forwarding packets through their leaf ports. Our algorithm searches for alternative, better paths only when congestion occurs. Some load balancing solutions, such as [14], store alternative paths in advance and switch to them when congestion is detected. We chose not to store alternative paths, as this would require more memory and constant checks to ensure the alternative paths are still uncongested. Instead, we switch paths only as a last resort, minimizing disruptions to flows. Path changes can lead to out-of-order packets, which are detrimental to TCP performance.

The learning process consists of two phases. In the first phase, controlled flooding of "learn packets" is initiated from the lower leaf switch. Each learn packet contains the flow's identifier and a strength field, which decreases when the packet passes through overloaded ports. The strength field is initially set to the maximum possible value. A switch processes a learn packet only if its strength field is greater than that of any previously received learn packet for the same flow, or if the earlier learn packet belongs to a previous learning process (verified by comparing timestamps, as discussed in Section III-D1).

When a non-leaf switch processes a learn packet, it records the current timestamp (to distinguish between learning processes), the ingress port (leading to the lower leaf switch), and the packet's strength. If path entry persistence is not possible, the learn packet is ignored. Finally, the learn packet is forwarded using split horizon, potentially reducing its strength field if the ingress and/or egress ports are congested.

The purpose of the learn packets is to find the fastest and least congested path from the lower to the upper leaf switch.

FIGURE 4: Propagation of learn packets (black arrows) and confirmation packets (yellow arrows) between lower (L) and upper (U) leaf switches. Pale arrows indicate already forwarded, while crossed-out arrows indicate dropped (late) packets. The colored circles symbolize learned ports.

Controlled flooding can discover the fastest path, but it only considers latency in one direction (from lower to upper leaf switch). Since our algorithm builds symmetric paths between leaf switches, we also consider the latency in the reverse direction, using the strength field to account for it.

When the upper leaf switch processes a learn packet, it updates its registers like other switches, but instead of forwarding the packet, it replies with a confirmation packet sent through the port from which the learn packet was received. The confirmation packet has the same strength as the learn packet. It travels in the reverse direction, from the upper leaf switch to the lower leaf switch, through the previously learned ports. As with the learn packet, switches process or drop the confirmation packet based on its strength, which is compared with the strength recorded in the flow's confirmation strength register. The learning process is complete when the last confirmation packet arrives at the lower leaf switch.

An example of how learn and confirmation packets propagate through the network is shown in Figure 4.

As previously mentioned, stale path entries may be deleted to free up memory for other entries. If only a few switches along a path delete a flow's entry and the flow becomes active again, packet loss could occur in very rare cases, especially for flows that only transmit data in one direction (e.g., from client to server). To mitigate this issue, as explained in Section III-D1, a learning process is initiated whenever MAC learning has not been completed for either MAC address of a flow. MAC learning can be performed using the learn and confirmation packets: the ingress port of the learn packet can be associated with the lower MAC address, and the ingress port of the confirmation packet can be associated with the

FIGURE 5: Handling of learn packets. Actions related to MAC learning are shown in blue, while path entry-related actions are in green.

upper MAC address. If MAC learning is not possible due to a temporary inability to persist data, a flag must be set in the learn/confirmation packet header indicating that the packet should not be used for MAC learning by the receiving switches. This flag serves the same purpose as dropping regular data packets when MAC learning is not possible: forwarding such packets without executing MAC learning could lead to network loops.

The complete handling logic for learn and confirmation packets is illustrated in Figure 5 and Figure 6.

E. DATA PERSISTENCE IN P4

For the proposed load balancing algorithm to function, it must associate data with specific MAC addresses or flow identifiers during MAC learning and while establishing flow-specific paths. Additionally, the algorithm must be able to read and update the stored data to facilitate packet forwarding and flow rerouting. Unfortunately, persisting data using the P4 data plane programming language is not straightforward: P4 lacks the standard associative containers (such as trees or hash maps) found in general-purpose programming languages. This limitation applies equally to associating data with MAC addresses and flow identifiers, so we will treat

FIGURE 6: Handling of confirmation packets. Actions related to MAC learning are shown in blue, while path entry-related actions are in green.

both cases as one.

A simple approach to associating data with flow identifiers in P4 is by indexing a register (a fixed-size array of data entries) using the hash of the flow identifier modulo the size of the register. However, this approach has a drawback: hash collisions (when two or more hashes produce the same index) are not mitigated. Only one of the colliding entries can be stored, leading to the loss of the others. Standard collision resolution techniques are not applicable in P4 due to its limitations. In some cases, such as counting network usage, collisions are not critical. However, in MAC or path learning, the persistent failure to store data for certain flows could result in packet loss or even complete loss of connectivity for some hosts.

An alternative approach in P4 is the use of built-in match-action tables. These tables map keys to actions and their associated parameters. The major disadvantage of this approach is that the data plane cannot modify the tables directly: only the control plane can add or update entries. One potential solution is to pair each switch with a local controller (a controller dedicated to that switch): switches can send messages to the local controller, instructing it to update the match-action table [31]. However, this communication between the data plane and the control plane introduces delays, which may result in the temporary inability to persist data, potentially causing packet loss, especially for the first few packets of a new flow.

To address these challenges, our proposed model combines both methods. When a new flow is detected, it is temporarily stored in a register indexed by the flow identifier's hash, while the local controller is instructed to reserve a unique key for the flow and map the flow identifier to this key in a match-

action table. Once the match-action table entry is inserted, the flow's data can be transferred from the temporary register to a different register indexed by the reserved key. If no hash collisions occur in the temporary register, data persistence is immediate, without packet loss.

This combined solution requires 26 bytes of SRAM per slot (flow) for the hash-indexed register, while the key-based storage solution demands 130 bytes of SRAM per slot. This difference arises because the key-based solution's match-action table must be copied (cloned) multiple times to support multiple queries during the processing of a single packet. The match-action tables use exact matching, therefore no TCAM is required.

The likelihood of hash collisions is minimal, as only newly initiated flows are at risk of collision: ongoing flows are stored in a separate register. Assuming the size of the register indexed by the hashed flow identifier is 10 MB, there needs to be at least $\sqrt{\frac{0.1\%}{100\%} * 2 * \frac{10^7 \text{ byte}}{26 \text{ byte}}} \approx 27$ flows being simultaneously started for a hash collision to happen with a 0.1% probability. Additionally, hash collisions only result in temporary packet loss, as the network automatically recovers.

F. FLOW REROUTING IN CASE OF CONGESTION

When congestion occurs at a switch's egress port, a new path is assigned to a selected flow. This section explains the criteria used to determine which flow should be rerouted among those passing through the port. Let F represent the set of all flows routed through a specific port, and let $\text{bitrate}(f)$ denote the bandwidth consumed by flow $f \in F$.

If no grace periods are active, and the congestion condition described in Section III-D1 is met during packet processing, the flow associated with the packet will be rerouted. Since a flow's bandwidth is proportional to its packet count, the probability of rerouting flow $f_x \in F$ is:

$$p_{f_x} = \frac{\text{bitrate}(f_x)}{\sum_{f \in F} \text{bitrate}(f)}$$

This formula shows that larger flows are more likely to be rerouted than smaller flows, enabling the algorithm to quickly reduce congestion by prioritizing the rerouting of high-bandwidth flows.

In some cases, rerouting a flow can cause congestion on its new path. This can lead to flows being repeatedly switched between the two paths. Grace periods help mitigate this issue by preventing recently rerouted flows from being rerouted again too quickly. While the algorithm does not guarantee that equilibrium will be reached within a finite time, it is designed to eventually create a stable, congestion-free network through probabilistic means.

The probability of rerouting a specific flow $f_x \in F$ can be further refined by accounting for active grace periods. Let $F' \subseteq F$ represent the set of flows that can be rerouted (i.e., those not subject to an active grace period). The revised probability is:

$$p'_{f_x} = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } f_x \notin F' \\ \frac{\text{bitrate}(f_x)}{\sum_{f \in F'} \text{bitrate}(f)} & \text{if } f_x \in F' \end{cases}$$

G. LOAD CAUSED BY THE LEARNING PROCESS

While the path learning process aims to reduce the load on congested switches, it also generates some network load due to the forwarding of custom packets. The following analysis estimates the worst-case excess load introduced by the learning process. The following notations are used:

- N : number of switches in the network (upper bound)
- S : number of distinct strength levels (constant in the source code)
- T_r : learn request sending grace period (constant in the source code)

We approximate the network load by calculating the upper bound on the excess packets and bits per second (pps and bps) that may be sent through each switch egress port. To calculate the worst-case scenario, we assume that each path learning request involves a different flow and results in a new learning process.

One source of excess load is the packet used to request a new learning process. During a time interval of T_r , each switch may generate one such packet, and each switch may also forward packets generated by other switches. In the worst-case scenario, a switch may be responsible for forwarding N such packets through a single port every T_r interval, as would occur in a chain topology.

A new learning process is initiated when a request packet reaches the lower leaf switch, causing the switch to send learn packets through all its ports. When a switch (that is not a leaf switch) receives a learn packet, it forwards it via split horizon if it is the first learn packet it has received for that flow or if the packet's strength exceeds that of previously received learn packets. This means each switch transmits at most S packets per learning process. Since at most N learning processes can be initiated during a time interval of T_r , the maximum excess load per port due to learn packets is $N \cdot S$.

When the upper leaf switch receives a learn packet, it replies with a confirmation packet. For each learning process, up to S confirmation packets may be generated and forwarded back to the lower leaf switch. As with the learn packets, each switch forwards at most $N \cdot S$ confirmation packets during each T_r interval.

In summary, each switch egress port may experience an excess load of up to $\frac{N(1+2S)}{T_r}$ pps. An actual maximum load can be calculated by using the following values from the open-source P4 implementation:

- Request packet size: 31 bytes
- Learn and confirmation packet size: 32 bytes
- $S = 2^4 - 1 = 15$ distinct strength levels
- $T_r = 1$ sec learn request sending grace period

Given these values and assuming a network with $N = 100$ switches, the upper bound of the excess load is approximately

3100 pps, or around 800 Kbps. In a network with 1 Gbps links, this represents an overhead of approximately 0.08%. This worst-case scenario assumes that all switches are involved in initiating and processing path learning processes simultaneously, which would rarely happen in practice.

Despite this overhead, the algorithm is designed to minimize additional network load while improving load balancing and preventing congestion. The slight increase in traffic is outweighed by the performance improvements gained through dynamic path adjustment and congestion avoidance, ensuring that the network remains efficient and responsive to changing conditions.

IV. EVALUATION

We compared our load balancing algorithm with several related works by utilizing the P4 data plane programming language, the P4C compiler [32], the BMv2 software switch [33], and the Mininet network emulator [34]. We measured the time required for the different algorithms to transmit a predetermined amount of data across a network with fixed bandwidth, while also tracking packet loss, out-of-order packets, and the latency of individual data packets. While Mininet introduces some performance overheads, the functional behavior of load balancing algorithms remain unaffected, and relative comparisons between the results can be made. To minimize the impact of background processes on our evaluation, we repeated each simulation scenario six times, retaining only the five best-performing iterations.

During the evaluation, we compared our algorithm to load balancing solutions based on the ARP-Path [15] and TCP-Path [17] algorithms. While our implementations retain the core features of the original algorithms (learning a path for each MAC-pair or each TCP flow), there are some differences in specific details: i) our ARP-Path implementation can learn from any Ethernet packet, and ii) our TCP-Path implementation uses custom packets to facilitate the learning process, rather than relying on *SYN* and *SYN+ACK* packets. Our algorithm, ARP-Path, and TCP-Path are all load balancing solutions that operate without a centralized controller. For a more comprehensive comparison, we also included centralized algorithms in the evaluation: ECMP and HULA.

A. SIMULATION SETUP

The network topologies illustrated in Figure 7 were used for evaluation. The complete 3-tier fat-tree topology was used exclusively for Flow Completion Time (FCT) measurements, while the easier-to-understand, smaller highlighted topology (the left pod) was used to analyze the detailed behavior of the different algorithms. These topologies were chosen to enable comparison with related works, among which HULA only supports tiered topologies. In most evaluation scenarios, all switches and links had identical characteristics. However, in some cases, we used an asymmetric topology, where half of the possible paths had reduced throughput, and the other half experienced increased latency. The exact properties of the topologies are shown in the figure.

FIGURE 7: The topologies used for evaluation consist of two main setups. The first is a complete 3-level fat-tree topology, where all links have a latency of 0.5 ms and a maximum throughput of 5 Mbps . The second is the highlighted left pod, which has both symmetric and asymmetric variants. In the figure, the ms values represent link latency, while the Mbps values indicate the maximum switch throughput. The gray values in parentheses correspond to the properties of the asymmetric variant.

Flow type	Flow count		Maximum Tx rate		
	Count	Ratio	One flow	All flows	Ratio
Small	8	20%	62,5 Kbps	0,5 Mbps	3,57%
Medium	28	70%	125 Kbps	3,5 Mbps	25,00%
Large	4	10%	2500 Kbps	10 Mbps	71,43%
Summary	40	100%	-	14 Mbps	100,00%

TABLE 2: Properties of the flow types and their distribution.

The hosts that are farthest apart form pairs (e.g., H1–H5) and transmit three different types of TCP flows in parallel. Table 2 shows the distribution of these flow types. To make the simulation results easier to interpret, each flow is configured to send a predetermined amount of data, and under ideal conditions, each flow completes in 30 seconds. Actual completion times are influenced by TCP’s congestion avoidance, the load balancing algorithm in use, and any packet drops that occur during the simulations.

B. FLOW COMPLETION TIMES

We measured the flow completion times of different load balancing algorithms under various network loads (at different used/available bandwidth ratios). The traffic distribution described earlier corresponds to a 70% network load. The results for different topologies are shown in Figure 8. It can be observed that ECMP and ARP-Path scale poorly compared to more advanced methods. TCP-Path and HULA scale differently depending on the topology, while our algorithm consistently performs well. With HULA, we observe some performance variance, which we attribute to limitations in our Mininet-based simulation setup.

FIGURE 8: Maximum flow completion times under different network loads in different topologies.

C. RESULTS AT 70% NETWORK LOAD

We further analyzed the simulation results at 70% network load in the smaller (pod) topology, examining the changes in transmission rate, latency over time, and the counts of dropped and out-of-order packets produced by the different load balancing algorithms. Figure 9a shows the transmission rates of switches and hosts over time in a symmetric network topology. The columns represent the different load balancing algorithms, while the rows correspond to different re-runs of the simulation.

It can be observed that our solution transmits the predefined amount of data in less time than some existing solutions (approximately 10% and 20% faster on average than ECMP and ARP-Path, respectively). It’s important to note that the performance of HULA and our solution is reliable; they remain consistent across multiple runs, with no significant differences in the time required to complete transmissions.

During the simulation runs, the ECMP, ARP-Path, and TCP-Path algorithms sometimes fully utilized the bandwidth of one of the paths: a single switch was occasionally responsible for forwarding data at 10 Mbps, the maximum capacity of the simulated switches. In reality, the load balancers attempted to forward more than 10 Mbps on these paths, resulting in packet loss. The TCP congestion avoidance algorithm responded to the packet loss by temporarily lowering the transmission rate of the flows, which can be observed as fluctuations in the hosts’ transmission rates (dotted lines). Additionally, the figure shows that when the transmission rate of one host decreases, the other host takes advantage of the freed-up bandwidth and increases its transmission rate.

Ideally, the sum of the Tx rates of the hosts and the sum of the Tx rates of the switches should equal the sum of the maximum transmission rates of the flows. This occurs when no packet loss is present, and TCP flows can transmit data at their respective Tx rate limits. We observe this behavior with both our algorithm and HULA: although the amount of data transmitted through switches S1 and S2 varies between runs, the combined Tx rates of the two switches always remain constant at 14 Mbps, matching the total simulation rate. In contrast, with ECMP, flows are sometimes distributed

unevenly between paths, such as in a 12 Mbps and 2 Mbps ratio. This leads to congestion and packet loss on the over-loaded path, while flows on the other path complete their transmissions faster, without packet loss. The ARP-Path algorithm sometimes demonstrates an extreme case of unequal distribution, where only one of the two paths is used, as it may learn the same path twice for both MAC pairs.

In the simulation results for our algorithm, there are cases where the Tx rates of the switches fluctuate significantly at the start of a run. This happens because, like other solutions, our algorithm occasionally selects the same path for too many flows initially. However, our algorithm quickly detects the resulting congestion and reroutes flows to alternate paths to alleviate it. Rarely, as seen in run #5, the rerouted flows cause congestion on the new path when they are combined with existing flows of the path. This results in further rerouting, which swiftly resolved the issue in run #5, establishing two congestion-free paths. HULA can also cause occasional fluctuations due to its design: if multiple new flowlets appear simultaneously (e.g., after timing out), they are all routed through the same, at that moment, ideal path.

We also analyzed the simulation results using an asymmetric topology. Similar to the previous figure, Figure 9b shows the Tx rates over time. The algorithms were more likely to select the route containing switch S2, as this route had a lower propagation delay in the asymmetric topology compared to the alternative route. ARP-Path exclusively learned this single path in all five simulation runs, limiting its transmission rate to 9 Mbps despite the network’s total bandwidth being 19 Mbps, resulting in high latency and packet loss. ECMP and TCP-Path also exhibited degraded performance. In contrast, our algorithm and HULA performed well despite the asymmetric topology, thanks to their dynamic path selection capabilities. In these simulation runs (with a 70% network load), our solution transmitted the predefined amount of data approximately 20%, 35%, and 5% faster than ECMP, ARP-Path, and TCP-Path, respectively.

Figure 10 shows the total delay experienced by individual data packets over time. With ARP-Path, the difference between minimum and maximum latency is relatively small

(a) Symmetric topology

(b) Asymmetric topology

FIGURE 9: The transmission rate of switches and hosts over time at 70% network load.

because all packets take the same path, and the length of the switch queues remains nearly constant. In contrast, ECMP and TCP-Path often show a wider latency distribution. Most packets experience high delays, but a few flows take an alternate, less congested, low-latency route. As a result, while the average delay is still high, a few packets experience minimal latency. In TCP-Path’s run #2 (among other runs), both the minimum and average delays increase sharply, because the flows routed through the less congested route completed their transmissions. Summarizing the runs, the average delays were approximately 45 ms, 50 ms, 30 ms, 10 ms, and 10 ms for ECMP, ARP-Path, TCP-Path, HULA, and our algorithm, respectively. While TCP-Path and our algorithm required roughly the same amount of time to complete the data transfer, our solution achieved much lower network delay and provided more consistent results.

Packet loss occurs when a switch’s queue is full (the switch is congested) and a new packet cannot be inserted. Figure 11 shows the number of packets that were transmitted but not received during the individual simulation runs. Our solution dropped fewer than 30 packets in each run. In contrast, ECMP, ARP-Path, TCP-Path, and HULA dropped approximately 420, 820, 70, and 40 packets on average, respectively.

Lastly, Figure 12 illustrates the number of packets received out of order for each algorithm. On average, ECMP, ARP-Path, TCP-Path, and HULA transmitted around 200, 330, 75, and 40 packets out of order, respectively. In the case of our algorithm, this number was less than 10. It is important to note that packet loss can also cause TCP packets to be marked as out of order due to the retransmission of lost packets.

D. RESULTS IN AN OVERLOADED NETWORK

We also measured how the different algorithms perform in a symmetric topology when the total Tx rate of the hosts

FIGURE 10: Network delay as a function of time.

FIGURE 11: Count of packets dropped due to filled queues.

FIGURE 12: Count of out-of-order packets.

exceeds the network’s bandwidth. The H1–H2 host pair transmitted 10 flows at 700 Kbps each, while the H3–H4 host pair transmitted 10 flows at 1750 Kbps each, resulting in a network load of approximately 120%.

Since the network load exceeds 100%, at least one of the two paths is always congested. Our algorithm, being unaware of this, continuously starts new path learning processes, constantly attempting to balance the flows between the two paths in an effort to eliminate congestion. This issue does not arise in the other load balancing solutions evaluated: ECMP, ARP-Path, and TCP-Path learn paths once and are unable to adjust them later, while HULA always selects the path that is optimal for the current flowlet at that moment.

The transmission rates over time for different simulation runs are shown in Figure 13. In terms of completion time, our algorithm on average outperforms ECMP, ARP-Path, and TCP-Path by approximately 35%, 45%, and 10%, respectively, while performing on par with HULA. It can also be observed that while ECMP, ARP-Path, and TCP-Path exhibit significant variation in their transmission completion times, our solution and HULA provide reliable, consistent results.

The figure shows that one host pair (transmitting the smaller 700 Kbps flows) finishes sooner than the other host pair (which transmits flows at a target Tx rate of 1750 Kbps). This is due to the TCP flow control algorithm: each flow receives a roughly equal share of the total available bandwidth, but the smaller flows’ bandwidth shares correspond to a higher percentage of their target transmission rates. As a result, while all the flows transmit roughly the same amount of data per second, the smaller flows have less total data to transmit and therefore finish sooner. When the smaller flows complete, the remaining flows can utilize the freed-up bandwidth and increase their transmission rates. This explains the spike in host H4’s transmission rate during the simulation runs.

The traffic overhead caused by HULA’s probe packets and the packets our solution uses for path learning was measured. As previously mentioned, at 120% network load, our solution continuously attempts to reroute flows due to overloaded switches, leading to frequent path learning requests and starts, which generate significant traffic overhead in this extreme scenario.

Despite this, our load balancing solution transmitted only 3,316 excess packets on average (1.10% of all transmit-

FIGURE 13: The transmission rate of switches and hosts over time at ~120% network load.

ted packets), while HULA’s probes caused an overhead of 6,533 packets (1.94%). By increasing the network bandwidth (while maintaining the network load at 120%), the number of excess packets would remain mostly constant, but the total packet count would increase, resulting in a lower traffic overhead percentage.

The other evaluated load balancing algorithms do not generate any traffic overhead.

V. CONCLUSION

We have introduced an algorithm capable of efficiently forwarding both unicast and multicast/broadcast packets in networks with unknown topologies, all without relying on a centralized controller or manual configuration. This algorithm dynamically balances network loads based on real-time conditions, responding to network congestion by intelligently rerouting some flows onto less congested alternative paths. This optimization of network bandwidth usage results in reduced latency and increased transmission rates for communicating hosts. Simulations have demonstrated that our algorithm outperforms other decentralized load balancing solutions and either matches or exceeds the performance of centralized alternatives. The algorithm has been implemented using the P4 data plane programming language, highlighting its practical feasibility.

In contrast to the self-organized load balancing algorithms discussed in Section II, our solution autonomously adapts to changing network conditions, including dynamic flow bandwidth requirements. Unlike the previous algorithms, which compute the optimal path only once when a new flow emerges, our solution can reroute ongoing flows. It supports any Ethernet-based network protocol (e.g., TCP, UDP) and can balance one-way (UDP-based) communication without requiring bidirectional packet exchange between hosts.

Moreover, our solution fully accounts for network latency in both directions, enabling load balancing even in adverse conditions, such as congestion or increased latency in one direction. The loss of packets used for path learning does not impact its reliability either: the algorithm continues to function effectively even in the event of packet loss.

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